

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D3.4 Three (3) Collaborathons Final Reports

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The co-creation process of the INTEGER project is a proof to the win-win dynamics inherent in our regional activities. The three regional Col·laborathons held in Hamburg, Krakow and Catalonia have served as pivotal milestones, fostering initial engagement with regional stakeholders and catalysing a learning journey crucial to model creation. Detailed in D4.1 (First draft of Comprehensive 3H & 4H Integration Innovation ecosystem model), these events facilitated ecosystem familiarisation and also enriched the co-creation process, nurturing a dynamic environment where diverse perspectives converged to drive INTEGER actions forward. These events promoted synergies, deepening our understanding of the different ecosystem landscapes, identifying needs and common goals. This has been achieved through:

- a) the connection of stakeholders across the Quadruple Helix (4H) spectrum and
- b) promote synergies between them (within and across regions) and also at European and international levels, accessing a better knowledge of their ecosystem landscape, namely the level of existing knowledge and interaction as well as the needs and gaps and common goals and vision.

INTEGER aims to strategically benefit stakeholders and beneficiaries, culminating in the creation of a model with outcomes such as active social innovation participation, wider access to financing and scalable, replicable innovation models. This collaborative approach underscores the project's commitment to mutual growth and sustainability.

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4. SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
4H	Quadruple Helix
EC	European Commission
HAM	BEHÖRDE FÜR ARBEIT, GESUNDHEIT, SOZIALES, FAMILIE UND INTEGRATION HAMBURG
UJ	UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLOŃSKI
KTP	KRAKOWSKI PARK TECHNOLOGICZNY SP ZOO
URV	UNIVERSITAT ROVIRA I VIRGILI

1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of this deliverable is to present the 3 Col·laborathons that successfully made it as the 3 top ranked projects selected in the 3 regional Col·laborathons. The document also details how the regional events went, namely the methodology, objectives, outcomes and lessons learned. These regional events provided a good opportunity to showcase common challenges and needs between stakeholders of the same region, as well as to link the regions between themselves and learn from their different contexts.

This document portrays how these events were organised and the results and impacts that came from them. Each region to piloted the incubation and acceleration of selected social projects using the INTEGER collaborative methodology, with special focus on the technology and business strategy support to individual projects, and dispute the common guidelines were the core of the actions each region has tailored their approach taking into account the specific needs from their stakeholders assessed in the consultation of key stakeholders and a browder group of stakeholders that step by step helped to unveil the landscape and the state of art of the social innovation ecosystem.

1.1 Background and aim

The deliverable is to access the final report of the three Col·laborathons, the presentation of the Col·laborathon and its challenges. The European Col·laboratory on Health and Wellbeing, is a transformative project born out of the collaborative efforts of three regions, Catalonia, Krakow and Hamburg, under the European INTEGER-4H initiative - Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions. This visionary undertaking, in conjunction with the broader *Col·laboratori Catalunya initiative* (Generalitat de Catalunya and I2Cat) marks a significant step forward in promoting social digital innovation. The INTEGER project organised, through its regional partners, with F6S coordination and support, 3 Col·laborathons (a collaborative quadruple helix Hackathon), one in each of the three regions of the project dedicated to the networking and exploration of innovative solutions to common challenges, through debates and presentation of proposals in pitch style to a pool of experts. The goal was to organise these initiatives in hackathon mode in each region, with actors from the social and business driven innovations and the quadruple helix spectrum working in the identified challenges.

The challenges were defined by each Region, taken into consideration the specific needs of its stakeholders and citizens. These thematic were the driver of a discussion that lead to a hackathon style competition that culminated into a pitch session presented to a pool of evaluators, experts in the regional thematic, that scored and selected one project, the highest scored, to be presented in a inter regional final event with all three regions, the Col·laborathon final event on the 17th of January that gathered key stakeholders and INTEGER partners, where these 3 regional proposals were once again presented and scored by a pool of diverse experts in social innovation. More than a competition the goal was to debate, present and reflect on challenges and potential solutions that can fit multiple regions. Strengthen the notion of community as well and widening the network and views beyond their own regions.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable starts by explaining the common guidelines that kick-started the process followed by the description of the methodology of implementation at a regional level, as well as the results, impact, and conclusions of the regional Col-laborathons.

The photos illustrate the event and participants dynamic, reflecting in images what was the opportunity that was created through these events for a community to gather around a regional identified common challenge and that results into a fertile soil of discussion about existing solutions being implemented or solutions that are proposed, either as a promoter of synergies and a better understanding of the social innovation ecosystem in their region.

The deliverable also presents the results and the solutions proposed as a valuable outcome that can have a sustainable impact in the project and in their communities, as the validation and support of the project may help to create financing opportunities to move forward with the development of the solution.

1.3 Methods

Overall, the methods used to organise and implement the Col-laborathons had common guidelines that were implemented in all three Col-laborathons, however, and taking into account the diverse maturity and starting point identified in the three regions, the implementation methods were adjusted to each region to fit best the ecosystem characteristics and needs.

As a quick start F6S prepared a Key stakeholders event that promoted a debate on the regional needs followed by regional events to identify the challenge that would be used as the umbrella thematic for organisation of the Regional Col-laborathons. This process is more detailed and reported in the D2.2 Col-laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan.

The methods followed balanced inputs pre-event, to experts' presentation and debates from stakeholders regarding common challenges, culminating, in all three regional events, into a hackathon presentation of solutions that were evaluated and received feedback from a pool of regionally selected experts in social innovation and relevant fields to the thematic of the regional event. We have also promoted the use and added value for stakeholders in the INTEGER platform, not only for exchange of information, as well as for contact internally, for partners and externally with stakeholders, promoting the inter-regional relations, as well.

Another relevant method to highlight was the one-on-one contact, more personalised, that started with the mapping of the stakeholders from the part of regional partners and led to a more direct contact between the regional partners and the stakeholders. These tailored contacts promoted and strengthened the relation with stakeholders from the ecosystem, promoting engagement of these stakeholders that would promote and pass on the word about the relevance and interest of INTEGER initiatives attracting more stakeholders and widening the INTEGER network.

Events online, hybrid and presidential also enabled a deeper contact between stakeholders and an open space for exchanges of ideas, namely in the INTEGER platform. By also preparing pre-events in native language for regional groups of stakeholders, as a first step, as it happened in

Hamburg for example, stakeholders were given an opportunity to know more about the added value of this project initiatives and it's goals and the agents involved in a more "familiar" context, leading them to more international, English speaking events and an inter-regional event, with the Final event for the Col·laborathon.

There was a use of dynamic tools that will be developed later on in the document by each region description provided, as well as a common tool to be used by stakeholders in order to present, discuss and take out conclusions in a clear and resumed way, showing as well the added value that the stakeholders could can take from the event and implement in some cases in their project, adjusting needs and tackling methods to overcome challenges and even identify potential partners in the region and not only to be able to have a higher impact in the ecosystem.

1.4 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

This deliverable is linked with the actions developed earlier in the project on the context of the WP2 (*LEARNING FOR 4H COLLABORATORY CO-CREATION*), namely the Task 2.4 Col·laborathon results exploitation M5-M24, lead by F6S with the participation of the regional partners, as URV, i2CAT, HAM, KTP, UJ. The goal of this task sets the base of the actions that lead to the 3 regional Col·laborathon results, as it allowed the "**collecting of solutions** proposed, **synthesising lessons learned** and **implementation of actual actions** to generate scenarios for the bi-directional inclusion of socio-digital innovators and entrepreneurs in innovation ecosystems (synergies development between ecosystems in the field of smart ageing systems)", as determined by the INTEGER Grant Agreement (101096563).

Also, within the WP3 (*REGIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS' AS COLLABORATORY TESTBEDS*), led by URV, the several tasks added value and contributions to the development of the regional events. The Task 3.2 **Organisation and implementation of one Col·laborathon, as the source of actions that lead to this deliverable, as it had a goal in each region to pilot the incubation and acceleration of selected social projects. It also stresses the need to use the INTEGER collaboratory methodology, already planned in the WP2 previous task, as well as in WP4 several actions, as it has the goal of articulating *into long-lasting initiatives a model of bi-directional inclusive dynamics and mechanisms of workable processes of social innovation actors' integration into local and regional innovation ecosystems, transferring INTEGER experience at European and broader levels.***

Figure 1. The enfolding of actions that promoted synergies between the several WP's

By combining the several tasks from WP3 the focus remain on the technology and business strategy support to individual projects through the **event design and implementation, as well as through the** hands-on training through short training pills to Col-laborathons participants ex., socio-digital entrepreneurs/innovators (business models, company creation, exploitation plans) and ecosystems managers training (European public policy, economic and societal impact, Human-Centred Design, Inclusion, citizenship, and awareness, etc.) and the piloting the incubation and acceleration of selected social-digital projects via regional, that will enable the selection of three best social projects at each region (URV, HAM & UJ), through the validation and evaluation of experts from the 3 regions, through a final online pitching session for projects presentation, Q&A and selection, in a final event that gathers all the 3 regions.

Actions in both contexts of WP2 and WP3 have contributed as well to the construction of the collaborative model in WP4 (INTEGER 4H MODEL & EU HEALTHY LIVING COLLABORATORY DEPLOYMENT), lead by I2Cat, as it contributed to the goal of the goal of this WP, providing “systematisation of relevant information and material in the INTEGER platform hub (ex. Societal challenges and needs as identified by the col.laboratory dynamics and other regions dynamics; existing entrepreneurs and social innovators in the field”, as well as starting initiatives that enabled the interconnecting and exchange with the related initiatives and networks.

To enhance the impact of these activities, the consortium members tailored a variety of dissemination and communication efforts. Dissemination involved sharing project-related knowledge with relevant stakeholders and other interested parties, including the general public, at local, national, European, and international levels, in a constant collaborative work with WP5.

The below table shows how the link between the actions previewed in the several WP and tasks build a timeline that feeds each event and that culminates into a final event that took place in Month 12 of the INTEGER project. A step-by-step methodology that valued

the stakeholders input and led to the model construction from WP4 as well as an impact and sustainable result for the project.

Figure 2. The Timeline and synergies between Task 2.4, Task 3.2 and Task 3.3

2 Krakow Col-laborathon

2.1 Brief overview of the Col-laborathon

The Col-laborathon was organised as an important part of the conference Life Science Open Space (<https://lsos.info/>), held in KPT on **29th November - 1st December 2023**. Krakow Technology Park and Jagiellonian University, in collaboration with the Life Science Krakow Cluster, has created a unique event that serves as a platform for collaboration among students, seniors, business professionals, administrators, and academic individuals.

The Col-laborathon itself, entitled as the AHathon (<https://ahathon.lifescience.pl/>) (Active Healthy Ageing) in the Malopolska Region has brought together the co-creation process to stakeholders of quadruple helix. Krakow Technology Park, traditionally associated with technological innovations, has ventured into a new area – social innovations. Having great experienced partners in the topic of social innovations such as Jagiellonian University only helped to make that event an inspiring and successful one.

2.2 Key objectives and outcomes

Key objectives

Idea of combining the regional Col-laborathon with an already well-known and established conference in the Malopolska Region happened to be a big success. Thanks to that we have been able to create an outstanding critical mass for the whole event. Bringing together as wide an audience as possible has been the **key objective** from the very beginning and it was delivered with flying colours, as during those 3 days event we have gathered more than **300 unique attendees**. Moreover, the vital role of the stakeholders of quadruple helix played an important part as

another objective. In addition to that, **publicity about the INTEGER project** has also been one of the objectives.

Outcomes

Those one went far beyond the actual purpose, as thanks to the collaboration held during the event there have been created 5 bright ideas for social innovations amongst which one will be implemented as a pilot project in one of the municipalities in the Malopolska Region. In addition to that, all the teams have gained a financial reward, and the winning one, also the mentoring programme. Moreover, there is a possibility to implement the winning idea into one of the municipalities in the Malopolska Region. That great cooperation with the municipality was also very helpful during the Special Interest Group meeting (description below).

2.3 Host organisation and collaborators

The whole event (Col-laborathon and the conference) was held in the headquarters of Krakow Technology Park (60 Podole Street, Kraków). In addition to that the additional space was offered (for the second day of work, 30th November) for the teams to develop their ideas (14 Bobrzyńskiego Street, Kraków).

2.4 Duration and schedule

The duration and schedule were according to the images below:

AHATHON				LSOS DAY 1				LSOS DAY 2				
ENTERPRISE 1+2		SHOWROOM	GALAXY (ENTERPRISE 1	ENTERPRISE 2	ATRIUM	SHOWROOM	GALAXY	ENTERPRISE 1	ENTERPRISE 2	ATRIUM	SHOWROOM
WEDNESDAY 29.11.2023				THURSDAY 30.11.2023				FRIDAY 01.12.2023				
Hours				Hours				Hours				
9:00	REGISTRATION			9:00	WELCOME / KEYNOTE (Hans Hofstraat)				9:00	KEYNOTE - Active Healthy Aging (Akos Wetters)		
9:30	Active Healthy Ageing - WELCOME			9:30	INTRO/ DISCUSSION	SESSION KEYNOTE			9:30	INTRO/ DISCUSSION	PANEL DYSKUSYJNY	
10:00				10:00	HOSPITAL OF THE FUTURE	LIFESTYLE			10:00	DRUG DISCOVERY/ DEVELOPMENT	STARTUP SCENE	AHATHon presentations
10:30				10:30					10:30			
11:00				11:00	COFFEE BREAK				11:00	COFFEE BREAK		
11:30	Workspace	CHILL Out	SALA DLA MENTORÓW)	11:30	INTRO/ DISCUSSION	LIFESTYLE			11:30	INTRO/ DISCUSSION	STARTUP SCENE	AHATHon presentations
12:00				12:00	PERSONALIZED MEDICINE	PANEL			12:00	ADVANCED THERAPIES? - TBC	PANEL DYSKUSYJNY	AHATHon JURY settlement
12:30				12:30					12:30	COFFEE BREAK		
13:00	LUNCH WILL BE SERVED			13:00	LUNCH				13:00	COFFEE BREAK		
13:30				13:30					13:30	PANEL and WRAPUP		
14:00				14:00	INTRO/ DISCUSSION	BUSINESS & CAREER DEVELOPMENT			14:00			
14:30				14:30	DIGITAL HEALTHCARE				14:30			
15:00				15:00					15:00			
15:30				15:30	COFFEE BRAKE				15:00+			
16:00	Workspace	CHILL Out	SALA DLA MENTORÓW)	16:00	INTRO/ DISCUSSION	BUSINESS & CAREER DEVELOPMENT						
16:30				16:30	VISUALIZING HEALTH							
17:00				17:00								
17:30				17:30	COFFEE BRAKE							
18:00				18:00								
18:30				18:30								
19:00				19:00+	INSPIRATIONS (Ingmar Hoerr / CureVac) / ATRIUM							

Figure 3. The agenda for the 3 activity days in Krakow Col-laborathon

2.5 Workshops, sessions, and activities

Three days that were dedicated for the engagement of the stakeholders and step by step evolution of the networking and debate solutions, common needs and challenges.

AHathon, 29th November 2023

That day was dedicated to the co-creation and collaboration workshop for social innovations. All went according to the schedule (see agenda below, point 2.10). The whole concept was based on the design thinking methodology as many of the facilitators from KPT and UJ are experts in that field. The conference space has been designed to come across creative thinking with leisure corners, educational facilities. The teams have been briefed and informed about the rules.

All the criteria have been presented to the teams by representatives of KPT and UJ. There has also been time for the questions and enquiries regarding the criteria. Moreover, all participants learnt about the INTEGER project, partners and the aim of the project. Additionally, the concept of hackathon has been explained to the audience. It was an important remark as the scheme of idea development of social innovations is very similar to those one while working in a traditional form of hackathon. Then there was time for the team work. There was one break planned for lunch. The rest of the time was flexible for the teams. Yoga classes and coffee have also been offered for the teams. The end of the work for 29th November was planned at 8 pm and some of the teams used that time for their project development.

The teams have been offered the opportunity to continue their work on 30th November in the Klaster LifeScience premises. A few teams used that one and developed their ideas, presentations and pitches. It should be emphasised here, that thanks to the joint effort of the organisers, the teams of different ages were formed to ensure interdisciplinarity and diversity of perspectives. The age range of the teams included people aged 23-82.

LifeScience Open Space, day 1, 30th November 2023

Life Science Open Space is the forum for dialogue on the region's smart specialisations. It is also an international meeting of professionals, fans and users of technologies and innovations for health and quality of life. The whole conference took place in the Krakow Technology Park premises. The conference has been divided into thematic tracks and one of them designed and coordinated by KPT and UJ and dedicated to the broad theme of lifestyle. During that track the audience learnt about the power of habits, healthy and responsible eating. The track was a combination of pitches and panel discussions. Moreover, during that event the Krakow team organised a special meeting designed to introduce the Col-laborathon model (established within the INTEGER project). The meeting took place on 30th November. During the meeting representatives of local, regional, national authorities responsible for social affairs, the Regional Centre for Social Policy in Cracow, activists and NGOs discussed how to improve the model from the regional perspective. The aim objectives of the co-creation session were to share views and opinions on:

1. Why do we need a quadruple helix col-laboratory model?
2. How the INTEGER col-laboratory can help me?

3. Provide feedback to presented the Col-laborative Model.

During the workshop the participants were asked to share their best practises they were involved in or heard on a topic of social and technology synergies and reflect on the presented Col-laborative Model. The co-creation session was based on pre-prepared canvases presenting the Col-laborative Model and representatives of quadruple helix actors shared their reflections and new recommendations to each module by writing their comments on post-its and then sticking them to the canvas hung in the room. The workshop delivered the collective knowledge on different activities undertaken by local, regional and national level of administration (the governor office) acting in Malopolska region in the area of health and social policy strategies and social aid care. That happened through short presentations of 3 living labs involved in piloting collaborative model and key the meeting was finalised with an open discussion on Collaboratory model, key findings how to adjust it to regional needs and both joint declarations to support the implementation of the Collaboratory model through Special Interest Group focused on Active Healthy Aging. The participants of the meeting declared their support in Col-laboration model deployment and offered their participation in regular meetings of the Special Interest Group of Active Healthy Aging (SIG AHA).

The meeting happened to be very fruitful with many insights of how to make that model event better and more suitable for the regional context.

LifeScience Open Space, day 2, 1st December 2023

The second day of the conference was particularly important for the AHathon teams as it was a day of the pitches. On a dedicated stage all five teams had a chance to present and pitch their ideas for social innovations in accordance with the challenge presented on the very first day of AHathon. After the presentation the jury had a meeting to decide which idea and solution will win meaning it meets the best criteria of the best project selection and has the most MVP readiness level. The winning team was offered, besides financial award, the mentoring sessions. The main prize was transferred to the Sasiadex team (the name of the team), which presented the most complex design solutions improving older people's communication and integration through the use of neighbourhood assistance resources. The mentoring will start at the very beginning of 2024 and additionally there will be a possibility to start the process of implementation in municipalities in Malopolska Region. Additionally, the jury decided to award four parallel financial prizes for the remaining teams.

2.6 Overview of participants

All the stakeholders of quadruple helix were presented during the event (including students, business, academia, pensioners, public administration). 5 teams were presented during the AHathon and they also delivered the pitches during the final day of the conference.

Figure 4. The graphic with the overall participants per sector

2.7 Description of challenges or themes addressed

The main challenge was identified finally as: How to tap the potential of the ageing population in the regions, especially in cities?

We are a society that gets older every year. This is an inevitable and dynamic process that has a huge impact on various spheres of social, economic and political life. This poses a number of challenges, but also opens up space for new opportunities for development and innovation.

The exact challenge posed to AHathon participants was: "How to realise the potential of the ageing population in the regions, especially in cities?".

2.8 How challenges were selected

Poland is one of the fastest ageing societies in the EU, and population ageing is not only a global challenge, but it is especially visible at the local level. Insufficient use of the potential of the ageing population means wasting their experience, knowledge and skills. Social innovation can be a way to activate the elderly, thus bridging barriers and social exclusion in many areas (e.g., digital, architectural, labour market). In today's dynamic and unpredictable world, is it possible to implement innovative solutions in the areas of the labour market, health situation and social inclusion that meet the challenges of demographic change at the local and international levels?

Thanks to that demographic aspect the AHathon challenge got a chance to answer the real needs for an ageing population.

This situation caused the challenge chosen for the AHathon was about solutions based on the real need for an ageing population.

2.9 How teams were formed

The teams have been formed during the registration process. Nevertheless, during the event the teams have been mixed in accordance with the principles of design thinking methodology (diverse teams). All the participants have been willing to join their new teams and as a result great ideas have been created.

2.10 Team dynamics and collaboration

All registered participants got the agenda (see below) for the following work a few days before the event. The moderation and facilitation have been offered during the whole event. Yoga classes, lunch, coffee breaks have also been delivered for the participants.

All the teams learnt about the challenges and rules of the assessment of the projects. On the very beginning of their cooperation the members had a chance to present themselves briefly,

Agenda	
Od 9:00	Welcome coffee
9:30 – 9:40	Dzień dobry i dlaczego tu jesteśmy? Kazimierz Murzyn, Fundacja Klaster Life Science
9:40 – 9:50	Skąd tyle logotypów? O projekcie poza granicami Mateusz Kowacki, Krakowski Park Technologiczny
9:50 – 10:00	O hacathonach jako takich Sonia Bazan, Krakowski Park Technologiczny
10:00 – 10:20	Kryteria i cel i dlaczego nagroda jest taka wysoka? Kazimierz Murzyn, Fundacja Klaster Life Science Mateusz Kowacki, Krakowski Park Technologiczny Dr hab. Jolanta Perek-Białas, Centrum Ewaluacji i Analiz Polityk Publicznych UJ Joanna Kwinta-Odrzywołek, Centrum Ewaluacji i Analiz Polityk Publicznych UJ
10:30 – 18:00	AHathon
BONUS!	
13:00	Pyszny lunch
9:00 – 18:00	Pyszna kawa i inne napoje
14:00 – 16:00	Joga dla chętnych

Figure 5. The agenda of the 29th November provided to regional participants

2.11 Tools, frameworks, or methodologies used during the Col·laborathon

The design thinking methodology was ideal for that kind of work which was planned during the AHathon. Based on the experience of the Krakow team (KPT and UJ) that methodology guaranteed the best cooperation of that diverse team. All the facilitators of the process have been professionally trained in that area as it guaranteed the best level of work during the workshops. As an inspiration all the teams have been informed about the principals and rules of 'good work' during the AHathon and additionally about the challenges which happened to be extremely important.

2.12 Overview of projects developed

The challenge (identified as: How to tap the potential of the ageing population in the regions, especially in cities?) was taken up by representatives of different backgrounds and different generations. Participants, in multi-generational teams, worked on ideas for solutions to social problems, particularly problems related to communication - both concerning effective access to information (cultural, sports, local) and related to transportation constraints.

2.13 Key features of selected projects

All the ideas presented were characterised by the following features:

- response to a real social need and adequacy of the solution to the needs,
- intergenerational cooperation,
- innovation,
- replicate to broader population, other regions/cities,
- benefits in the Active Healthy Aging domain.

2.14 Criteria for judging projects

The experts that were part of the pool of evaluators were:

- Monika Machowska, KRAKOWSKI PARK TECHNOLOGICZNY SP ZOO (KTP);
- Kazimierz Murzyn, Council at Sano, Centre for Computational Personalised Medicine – International Research Foundation;
- Jolanta Perek-Białas, UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI (UJ);
- Agnieszka Włodarczyk-Gębik, KRAKOWSKI PARK TECHNOLOGICZNY SP ZOO (KTP);

Judging projects were selected with 3 main criterias:

- 5. Concept & innovation,**
- 6. Sustainability & replicability,**
- 7. Impact**

The additional questions which were taken into consideration were:

- *What is the objective and the resolution of your solution? Please focus specifically on how the social and the business-driven innovations can join forces to engage in a clear implementation and the possible solution to be used.*
- *Who is the target audience of your solution?*
- *What change will this solution bring, as an added value for the well-being and healthy living ecosystem?*
- *What are the synergies that will be implemented in the 4Helix to contribute to the solution implementation?*
- *Is your solution sustainable & replicable?*
- *In what way your solution replies to the SDG goals?*

2.15 Any follow-up initiatives or plans

The winning solution was offered 14 hours of professional mentoring (AHA content, business development, etc) and financial award for pilot implementation (the amount/size of financial award to be defined).

2.16 Quotes or feedback from participants, mentors, or organisers

The aim of the AHATHON is not only to test social innovations and try to answer the challenge established by project partners, but to raise the interest of a varied group of stakeholders representing quadruple helix on the implementation of fully accepted joint Collaboratory model. Using our previous experience in the area of social innovation we created a critical mass of the projects, ideas and teams as big as possible. Having that critical mass will guarantee easy dissemination and possibly commercialisation of the ideas presented. That's why we started our promotional campaign for AHATHON in August 2023. Thanks to the cooperation with Life Science Cluster in Krakow we joined forces during their event on *Life Science Open Space* (<https://lsos.info/>). The forum of mentors, facilitators, and topic specialists will be involved in the process of selection of the best solutions which will be developed during AHATHON.

All the presentations were at a very high level and seduced us with their ideas. Therefore, we chose one group as the winner, and the rest of the teams received equal prizes.

2.17 Additional materials, charts, or data

The additional material is presented in the form of photos took during the **AHathon, 29th November 2023**

Figure 6. LifeScience Open Space, day 1, 30th November 2023

Figure 7. LifeScience Open Space, day 1, 30th November 2023 - SPECIAL INTEREST GROUP meeting. INTEGER's model consultations with regional stakeholders

Figure 8. LifeScience Open Space, day 2, 1st December 2023. Pitches of the AHATHon teams

2.18 News on INTEGER website and social media

The dissemination managers together with the Polish partners have prepared news to disseminate the event on the INTEGER website and social media.

INTEGER - Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in...
 324 seguidores
 2 m · 1

🌟 Exciting Update from the Life Science Open Space Conference in Krakow! 🌟

On November 30th, as a significant segment of the conference, a SPECIAL INTEREST GROUP (SIG) session took place, adding another layer of depth to the INTEGER project's journey. Hosted by our esteemed partners at **Krakowski Park Technologiczny | Krakow Technology Park**, this session was a meeting of minds, gathering regional stakeholders to delve into the innovative INTEGER model of cooperation.

The primary aim was twofold: first, to present the robust **#INTEGER** model and, second, to actively engage with stakeholders, gathering their invaluable feedback for enhancing and refining this model further. The event was a testament to the commitment of all involved in ensuring that INTEGER evolves to meet the diverse needs and dynamics of different regions.

This gathering served as a crucial platform within the Life Science Open Space conference, providing an opportunity for stakeholders to share insights, perspectives, and suggestions for improving the INTEGER model. Krakow Technology Park's initiative in organizing this meeting showcased a dedication to fostering collaborative, inclusive, and adaptable models of cooperation.

The insights gathered during this session will be pivotal not only in refining the INTEGER model but also in complementing the learnings from similar workshops held in Hamburg and Catalonia. The regional nuances and feedback collected across these workshops will significantly enrich the INTEGER project, empowering it to thrive in various contexts and regions.

This collaborative effort exemplifies the essence of the INTEGER project – a convergence of ideas, expertise, and regional insights to create a model that resonates across boundaries. Here's to the collective progress achieved through such collaborative endeavors! 🌟🌟 **#LifeScienceOpenSpace #INTEGERProject #Collaboration #Innovation**

Carina Dantas, Natália Machado, Inês Saavedra, Joana Vieira SHINE 2Europe Toñi Caro, Chris O. Moscardi Luzuriaga Rafael Nualart, Marcos Doespiritusanto Gallego, Willeke Van Staaldinien, Javier Ganzarain, Jonas Bernitt AFEdemy, age-friendly environments academy, Uniwersytet Jagielloński w Krakowie, Xavier Camara-Turull Universitat Rovira i Virgili Kai Schnackenberg, Rachel Stenner, Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg, Monika Machowska, Agnieszka Włodarczyk, Mateusz Kowacki, Lina Silveira, F65

Figure 9. SHINE publication on Krakow Regional Col-laborathon, from November 30 in Linked In

AHATHON Krakow Showcases INTEGER's Innovative Spirit

By Frederico / November 30, 2023

The AHATHON, held on November 29th in Krakow, Poland, unfolded as an exceptional testament to innovation, orchestrated within the dynamic framework of the INTEGER project. This event marked a pivotal milestone in exploring and harnessing the innovative potential embedded within INTEGER.

Central to INTEGER's ethos is its visionary approach—a proven innovation model designed to expedite the integration of social innovation actors and digital business entrepreneurial hubs across three EU regions. The AHATHON served as a vibrant stage, where INTEGER's principles came to life, fostering collaboration and ideation among diverse teams.

Guided by Krakowski Park Technologiczny | Krakow Technology Park, six dynamic teams comprising students, business representatives, and seniors embarked on a journey to conceptualize social innovations. Their dedication and collective expertise showcased the power of collaboration within the INTEGER framework.

This event not only demonstrated practical application but also emerged as a pivotal testbed for scaling and replicability across regions and fields. The ideas germinated during these intense two days hold immense potential not just for implementation but also for shaping policy actions that advocate active and healthy ageing.

Additionally, on November 30th, the conference featured a SPECIAL INTEREST GROUP (SIG) session, adding depth to the INTEGER project's journey. Hosted by Krakowski Park Technologiczny | Krakow Technology Park, this meeting of regional stakeholders aimed to delve into the innovative INTEGER model of cooperation.

The session's dual focus was to present the robust #INTEGER model and actively engage stakeholders, gathering invaluable feedback for further enhancement. It stood as a testament to the commitment of all involved in evolving INTEGER to meet diverse regional needs and dynamics.

This gathering, part of the Life Science Open Space conference, provided a platform for stakeholders to share insights and suggestions, enriching the INTEGER project with regional nuances and feedback.

The collaborative efforts in Krakow align seamlessly with the essence of the INTEGER project—a convergence of ideas, expertise, and regional insights to create a model resonating across boundaries. Such collective progress through collaborative endeavours promises a future where innovation thrives hand-in-hand with inclusivity and adaptability.

Congratulations to all contributors for making the AHATHON a resounding success within the INTEGER project! Your innovative ideas and collaborative spirit are propelling us toward a future where social innovation and digital entrepreneurship seamlessly intersect for the betterment of our communities.

Stay tuned for more updates on the continued evolution of INTEGER's innovative journey, enriched by collaborative regional insights and expertise.

Figure 10. SHINE publication on Krakow Regional Col-laborathon, from November 30 in INTEGER website

3 Hamburg Col-laborathon

3.1 Brief overview of the Col-laborathon

The Hamburg Col-laborathon was divided into four single events, one online workshop; one starts up-pitch in October; a full workshop day and a second start-up pitch in November 2023. The planning, agenda and speakers can be viewed in the following images, a document that was created to present an overview of the Col-laborathon.

 INTEGER

Save the Dates:
Hamburger Living Lab für soziale Innovation

Sehr geehrte Damen und Herren,

das Referat Innovation und Internationales des Amtes für Gesundheit der Sozialbehörde lädt Sie ein, das **Hamburger Living Lab für soziale Innovation** mitzugestalten! Unsere Vision: Akteur:innen aus Zivilgesellschaft, Wissenschaft, Wirtschaft und Politik bilden gemeinsam ein Ökosystem, in dem soziale Innovationen gemeinsam gedacht, entwickelt und verwirklicht werden.

Begonnen hat die Arbeit im Hamburger Living Lab für soziale Innovation im Frühjahr 2023. **Am 6. Oktober von 11 bis 12.30 Uhr** möchten wir bei einem Online-Treffen bereits aktive und neue Stakeholder zusammenbringen, um die Grundlage für die weitere Zusammenarbeit an unserem Living Lab zu festigen. Die Veranstaltung wird online auf MS-Teams stattfinden. Um teilzunehmen, folgen Sie bitte diesem Link und nehmen über Ihren Browser oder die MS-Teams-App teil: [Hier klicken, um an der Veranstaltung teilzunehmen](#).

Wir werden Sie über den aktuellen Stand unseres Living-Lab-Vorhabens informieren und den Fahrplan für die kommenden Monate vorstellen. Diese Veranstaltung legt den Grundstein für alle interessierten Stakeholder:innen, die noch nicht in den Entwicklungsprozess involviert waren, dient aber auch der Vorbereitung auf einen **Co-Creation-Workshop am 3. November 2023**. Dort können sich Stakeholder aus den verschiedenen Helixen miteinander vernetzen, neue Ideen entwickeln oder an der bereits identifizierten Herausforderung arbeiten, die Kommunikation zwischen Sektoren und Akteur:innen des Hamburger Gesundheitsbereichs transparenter und besser zu gestalten. Das Programm wird durch Vorträge von Living-Lab-Expert:innen abgerundet.

Die Entwicklung des Hamburger Living Labs für soziale Innovation findet im Kontext des von der EU geförderten Projektes **INTEGER – Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions** – statt, an dem sich das Referat Innovation und Internationales beteiligt. Das Projekt zielt darauf ab, drei wichtige Innovationen für die Entwicklung robuster, nachhaltiger, inklusiver und integrativer EU-Innovationsökosysteme einzuführen:

Das **INTEGER 4 Helix Col-laboratory Modell**
eine EU-Kollaborationsgemeinschaft für Gesundheits-Projekte
ein neues Berufsprofil, den "Kollaborateur" oder "Kollaborationsmanager".

Weitere Informationen zu dem Projekt INTEGER finden Sie unter <https://integercollab.eu/>.

Wir freuen uns über Ihre Teilnahme Ihren Beitrag am Hamburger Living Lab für soziale Innovation! **Reichen Sie diese Einladung gerne an interessierte Kolleg:innen weiter!** Bei Fragen rund um das Hamburger Living Lab wenden Sie sich gerne an mich oder Kai Schnackenberg (kai.schnackenberg@soziales.hamburg.de)

Mit freundlichen Grüßen
Kai Fritze
kai.fritze@soziales.hamburg.de

 Funded by the European Union

Figure 11. Press release on Hamburg Regional Col-laborathon events

Workshop "Development of a Hamburg Living Lab for Social Innovation"

November 3 from 10:00 to 16:00 at Billstraße 80a, room 1103

Agenda

TOP	Time	Program item
1	10.00 - 10.15	Welcome and project presentation
2	10.15 - 10.45	Input federal and state initiatives on social innovation; Ms. Stobbe (Ministry for Economy and Innovation) and Mr. Unterberg (IFB Investment and Development Bank Hamburg)
3	10.45 - 11.15	Best practice Living Lab Bremen; Dr. Brand (Leibniz Institute)
	11.15 - 11.30	Coffee break
4	11.30 - 12:00	Best practice Living Lab Siegen; Mr. Taugerbeck (University of Siegen)
5	12.00 - 12:15	Best practice Living Lab Barcelona; Dr. Caro (i2cat)
	12:15 - 13:15	Lunch break
6	13.15 - 13.30	Introduction new job profile Collaborator; Mr. Ganzarain
7	13:30 - 14:30	Workshop: Developing the Hamburg Living Lab on Social Innovation
8	14.30 - 15.00	Input on sustainability of Living Labs, Mr. Taugerbeck (University of Siegen)
	15.00 - 15.15	Coffee break
9	15.15 - 15-45	Discussion: Getting concrete – what is the distillate of the workshop? Do we have a common ground for a Living Lab? What are our next steps?
10	15.45 - 16.00	Conclusion and farewell

Figure 12. The agenda for the 3 November in Hamburg Col-laborathon

3.2 Key objectives and outcomes

The objective was to identify stakeholders with valid and relevant solutions to address the main needs of the Hamburg social ecosystem. The outcome was to select in two rounds of start-up pitches a Hamburg champion, so that this proposal could be presented in the final event from the 3 regional Col-laborathon, so that we could promote this regional proposal trans-regionally. The two workshops addressed the needs for the Hamburg stakeholder and after the topic living lab was selected how it can fit in the Hamburg ecosystem.

3.3 Host organisation and collaborators

All events were organised by the Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs and counted with the support of INTEGER partners, namely F6S as the task lead and URV as the WP3 leader.

3.4 Duration and schedule

As referred initially the Hamburg Col-laborathon was divided into four single events, adjusting also the events to the needs and maturity of the ecosystem, as it was still very in its initial stage of identification and knowledge of the stakeholders. Therefore, the duration of the events extended from October to November 2023, four single sessions done online, as well as in presence. The duration was adjusted taking into account the type of event, from a couple of hours to a full day. The two workshop days had the following agenda:

Online workshop 06.10.2023 11:00 12:30:

- Round of introductions
- Basic information on the project
- Overview of the activities to date
- Input on expectations for the on-site workshop on 03.11.2023

3.5 Workshops, sessions, and activities

The second workshop was a full day presence workshop on 3rd November in a representative location in Hamburg.

The event started with inputs about federal and state initiatives on social innovation; speakers from the Hamburg Ministry for Economy and Innovation from the IFB Investment and Development Bank Hamburg outlined relevant policies and support programmes to foster social innovation.

Meeting the stakeholders' needs to get practical examples of successful Living Labs, the event went on with three best practice presentations by Living Lab representatives from Bremen, Siegen and Barcelona (online).

In the afternoon, the stakeholders were divided into two groups, with the 4 helixes represented in both groups. In the groups, the participants discussed the following key questions and documented them on flipcharts:

- What added value can a Living Lab bring to the participating persons/organisations?
- How could a Hamburg Living Lab be organised?
- What resources are available and what other resources are needed?
- How can these resources be provided?

The aim was to develop a common understanding of what a Living Lab in Hamburg should look like. The added value of a Living Lab for each organisation was discussed in order to encourage stakeholder involvement in the development of Living Lab. By looking together at possible

structures and available resources, the participants developed and agreed on the next steps that need to be taken for the implementation of a Living Lab in Hamburg.

3.6 Overview of participants

Participants were invited from the 4 Helixes, namely from:

- Public administration: Hamburg Ministry of Economics, University Hospital Hamburg, etc.
- Private companies: Optimedis AG; Hamburg Investment Bank etc.
- Civil Society/NGO’s: Patriotic Society Hamburg, Working Group on Sustainable Health etc.
- Universities: Hamburg University of Applied Science, Leibniz Living Lab, University of Giessen etc.

	Work shop October	Work shop November	Pitch October	Pitch November
Public Authorities	6	7	9	6
University	3	4	5	4
Privat Sector	2	4	40	39
Civil Society	1	1	3	3

Table 1. The Hamburg Col-laborathon participants per sector, per event

As the entrance was free and the events were open we did not register the sectors of all participants just the total number: we had in total 12 participants on 06.10 and 18 participants on 03.11. On the two rounds of the pitch, we counted with six start-up companies that presented their solution for health innovation. On the first pitch we counted with 57 participants and on the second pitch with 54 people participating online.

Of the four events of the Hamburg Col-laborathon 139 people participated in total.

Figure 13. The Hamburg Col-laborathon online workshop on the 06.10.2023

3.7 Description of challenges or themes addressed

The challenge addressed is named “How to implement a Hamburg Living Lab”, as a result of the inputs provided by the key stakeholders of the regions and HAM orientation and validation.

The participants were divided into two groups, with the 4 helixes represented in both groups. In the groups, the participants discussed the following key questions and documented them on flipcharts. - What added value can a Living Lab bring to the participating persons/organisations? - How could a Hamburg Living Lab be organised? - What resources are available and what other resources are needed? - How can these resources be provided? The aim was to develop a common understanding of what a Living Lab in Hamburg should look like. The added value of a Living Lab for each organisation was discussed in order to encourage stakeholder involvement in the development of Living Lab. By looking together at possible structures and available resources, the participants developed and agreed on the next steps that need to be taken for the implementation of a Living Lab in Hamburg.

3.8 How challenges were selected

The first workshop took place on October 6th and was held online. In this workshop the stakeholders of the Hamburg region addressed their needs and expectations towards the Hamburg Living Lab but also the 2nd workshop that was planned as the main event of the Hamburg Col-laborathon. The stakeholders had a common understanding, that the Col-laborathon needs to address the Hamburg ecosystem and that the success of the INTEGER project in Hamburg is closely connected to developing a concrete vision of what the goal of the Hamburg Living Lab will be. The need of getting practical examples from successful Living Labs was also expressed by the stakeholders.

Figure 14. The Hamburg Col-laborathon posters for the pitching sessions in October and November

3.9 How teams were formed

A concern was to integrate a diverse representation in the teams, as we wanted to explore and present a better and more complete view over an issue and solution, therefore the teams were formed in a way that allowed us to represent as many helices as possible. Based on the registrations, the INTEGER project team was able to make a division, as it was known from which helices representatives were participating. This ensured that the perspectives of public administration, universities and the private sector were represented in the working groups. As

civil society was only represented by one person, this could only be represented in one working group

3.10 Team dynamics and collaboration

Working group 1:

Added value of a Living Lab in Hamburg: In order to generate added value, an analysis in the form of a survey was carried out in advance. The added value that arises is as follows:

- Low threshold offers for citizens in the neighbourhood
- Opportunity to introduce problem-oriented projects
- A discussion channel where different people can exchange ideas, but where specific issues can also be raised
- Platform to introduce topics but also as a "door opener"
- How a Hamburg Living Lab can be organised:
 - It is important that the Living Lab builds on existing structures
 - Neighbourhood based

Working group 2:

Added value of a Hamburg Living Lab can be generated if implemented in a very specific and located district (Leibniz Living Lab Bremen as a model). If these conditions are met, the following added value can result:

- Better and trustful access to target groups; bottom-up approach
- Sustainable structure (in contrast to projects)
- Networking opportunities
- The LL as a sustainable "vessel" from which projects originate but not a project itself
- Important structures:
 - Start with networking within the district, don't start too big
 - Pay attention to new players (possibly with private capital)
 - An unbiased view from the outside is necessary
- Financing:
 - An exploratory phase is necessary (in this phase, possibly find preliminary projects, partners, check constellations for cooperation). The exploratory phase could be financed by a foundation.
 - Should have many opportunities to try things out. However, this is difficult with public funds. Private funding should therefore be considered (e.g. foundations and private investors)

After the two working group presentations, the whole group started a fruitful discussion about how to concretely move on from this point. In the discussion, the following points were covered:

- The Poliklinik Veddel is currently setting up a district laboratory with researchers. They are already integrated into the district and are being partially funded.
- There are six local health centres in Hamburg. These probably do not have the resources to set up a Living Lab. However, they could be used as partners because they address a specific target group.

- Initially, corporations should only be with few selected players so that the project does not grow too quickly.
- Cooperation with a large number of health insurance companies should be avoided. In general, one should limit oneself to a few selected investors, as otherwise everyone will want to have a say.
- The INTEGER project can help the Hamburg stakeholders to lead the LL into an exploratory phase. This must be set at 2-3 years.
- Be careful with double structure: there already are several networks. The LL needs to stand out and have an individual focus.

3.11 Key features of selected projects

The Hamburg Col-laborathon was divided into two workshops and two start-up pitches. 6 start-up companies presented their innovative health solutions in two pitches October 11 and November 22 2023. A jury consisting of Kai Schnackenberg, Kai Fritze, and Marcus Falke rated the pitches regarding the categories Criteria & score system:

As a starting point for the evaluation overall, the proposals, if they are not a new project from the start, they have to present novelty and innovation. It may already have a working base, with running actions, however as a proposal it has to present novelty that can be at a strategic level, tools or implementation level, or other, in order to justify the need for support. The 3 main criteria have the same height and are to be assessed on the proposal to be scored from 01 to 05 by the external evaluators are the following:

Concept and innovation

Participants must demonstrate a clear set of objectives aligned with the definition of the goals and with the general objectives of the INTEGER project and the Col-laborathon challenge. Appropriateness of the project scope as the overall project vision. Quality, credibility, and clarity of project description. Interoperability level of the proposed solution. Innovation level, not only in a technical perspective, but also in a strategic and implementation perspective, as well as practices.

Sustainability and replicability

Quality, effectiveness and clarity of project activities and its sustainability & replicability. Alignment of the activities/actions with the INTEGER goals and the SDG. Presentation of milestones and means of verification.

Impact

The proposal must define its ambition and a clear set of expectations aligned with the objectives of the Col-laborathon. Proposals must demonstrate the impact of the proposal and its contribution. The ambition underlines the potential extent and overall impact of the proposal actions.

After rating the pitches, the start-up company “**help**” had received the highest scoring of all and was declared winner of the Hamburg pitch contest.

3.12 Criteria for judging projects

A pool of 3 evaluators were defined to evaluate the proposals, in the case of Hamburg these were the designated evaluators, expert in social innovation and part of the organisation of the event:

- Marcus Falke Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH;
- Kai Fritze Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs;
- Kai Schnackenberg Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs

As a starting point for the evaluation overall, the proposals, if they are not a new project from the start, they have to present novelty and innovation. It may already have a working base, with running actions, however as a proposal it has to present novelty that can be at a strategic level, tools or implementation level, or other, in order to justify the need for support. The 3 main criteria have the same height and are to be assessed on the proposal to be scored from 01 to 05 by the external evaluators, as indicated to the overall regions. The criterias are the following: Concept and innovation; Sustainability and replicability; Impact, as it was in the case of the other 2 regions.

3.13 Any follow-up initiatives or plans

As a result of the discussion during the Col-laborathon events it was planned the following next steps:

- Regular digital meetings but also meetings in person
- Agree on short and medium-term goals and milestones together
- Create a joint roadmap at the next meeting
- Next meeting second half of January
- The Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs sends invitation for the next meeting and shares the workshop documentation with all participants

It was recommended to all stakeholders to subscribe to the project platform INTEGER platform, “The Glocal Network” (<https://integer4h.theglocal.network/>), for further cooperation work.

3.14 News on the INTEGER website

The dissemination managers together with the Hamburg partners have prepared news to disseminate the event on the INTEGER website.

3.15 Next steps

The outcome of the workshop was as explained above the process of the creation of a Hamburg living lab around the initiative of the local *healöth centres* in the 7 districts of Hamburg. This idea was presented on the 15th December to 10 colleagues in the Ministry of Social Affairs Department for Health, who are in charge of innovation (local health centres, health literacy, health reporting, innovation in care, district health, digitization of healthcare). It was a common understanding that the initiative is of great value for Hamburg, and further steps were discussed. In the afternoon of the 15th December the results of the meetings and the plan on concrete steps to a Hamburg living lab could be presented to the director general for health of the Ministry of Social Affairs.

On the 26th January the next workshop took place with 13 participants who will all have an important role in the process of building up the living lab and concrete steps for this process were defined.

4 Catalonia Col-laborathon

4.1 Brief overview of the Col-laborathon

The Catalonia Col-laborathon, part of the INTEGER project, took place on November 22nd and brought together 76 previously registered and 56 attendees. The event lasted the entire day and showcased six innovative initiatives focusing on sustainable development, health, and community well-being. Participants engaged in workshops, talks, and a pitch contest, fostering collaboration, innovation, and collective learning.

4.2 Key objectives and outcomes

The main objectives included promoting collaboration, innovation, and collective learning. The event aimed to address societal challenges related to well-being, sustainability, and ageing. Outcomes included the presentation of six noteworthy projects, constructive feedback from evaluators, and the selection of the most outstanding initiative, the Healthy Cities Generator, as a catalyst for future innovative ideas.

4.3 Host organisation and collaborators

The event was organized under the INTEGER project, and key collaborators included Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú, Diputació de Barcelona, LivingLab IrsiCaixa, Valls Genera, and Bax & Company. Talks by Maite Fibla from Ship2B Ventures and Adrià Buzón from Cuideo provided valuable insights.

4.4 Duration and schedule

09:30 AM – Welcome and introduction to the INTEGER project. Rafel Nualart, i2CAT.

09:45 AM – Overview of the Col-laborathon, its proposal, and the day's schedule. Xavier Càmara, URV.

10:00 AM – Presentation of challenges and inspiring cases identified – identified initiatives. Rafel Nualart, i2CAT.

1. Community building. Networks, activities, and events
 - Alison Network. For the promotion of sustainable and healthy eating in neighbourhoods Rosina Malagrida
 - FIRABEC - Oriol Huguet
2. Digital Tools for wellbeing, health, and sustainability
 - MeMimaBaby - Albert Munné
 - Healthy Cities Generator (HCG) - Marta Rofin
3. Focus on Senior potentials and needs
 - SeniorLab - Karina Simieli
 - VR360 - David Gateu

10:40 AM – Table 1: Parallel Working Groups

6 working groups were formed, one for each presented case.

11:00 AM – Coffee break

11:20 AM – Table 2: Social Innovation Canvas

The Social Model Business Canvas has been used in each working group to find solutions to identified barriers and overcome them.

12:00 PM – Talk "Making change possible: innovative financing for impact projects" - Maite Fibla, Ship2B Ventures

12:30 PM – Table 3: Financing and Scalability Strategies
Groups have been discussing and proposing financial strategies and scalability plans for their projects.

01:10 PM – Talk "From economic benefit to social impact: business strategies with real social impact" - Adrià Buzón, Cuideo

01:50 PM – Standing lunch

02:45 PM – Table 4: Pitch Preparation
Creation and preparation of the pitch based on the MVP worked on.

03:30 PM – Pitch contest
Each group presented their project and the MVP developed during the morning workshops. This session provided a platform to share and demonstrate how the processes and dynamics proposed by INTEGER have been applied.

04:45 PM – Evaluation and closing of the day, questions and requests. Xavier Càmara, URV

05:00 PM – Farewell

4.5 Workshops, sessions, and activities

The Catalonia Col-laborathon, which occurred on November 22nd, began with a warm welcome and an introduction to the INTEGER project by Rafel Nualart from I2CAT. Xavier Càmara from URV then provided an overview of the event, outlining its proposal and the day's schedule. The morning session featured presentations of inspiring initiatives, such as community-building projects and digital tools for well-being, health, and sustainability. Working groups were formed to promote co-creation among stakeholders of the quadruple helix, focusing on identifying strengths, weaknesses, and overcoming barriers for long-term sustainability. Participants engaged in Social Innovation Canvas sessions to find solutions to the identified challenges. Talks by Maite Fibla and Adrià Buzón provided insights into innovative financing and impactful business strategies. The day concluded with a pitch contest, where each group presented their projects and MVPs, showcasing the application of processes proposed by INTEGER. Xavier Càmara wrapped up the event with an evaluation and closing remarks, emphasising the positive reception and the significant step towards promoting social and digital innovation in Catalunya.

Figure 17. Catalonia Col-laborathon of the 22 of November

4.6 Overview of participants

The event attracted 76 registrations, with 56 participants actively engaging in the Col-laborathon. Attendees included individuals from diverse backgrounds, fostering a multidisciplinary approach to addressing societal challenges.

Figure 18. Catalonia Col-laborathon participants per sector

4.7 Description of challenges or themes addressed

Challenges focused on sustainable development, health, and well-being in the community. Initiatives addressed emotional well-being among youth, healthy and sustainable eating, virtual reality experiences for the elderly, musical education for babies, urban health impact assessment, and redefining services for an ageing society.

4.8 How challenges were selected

The challenges aligning with the event's overarching themes were likely selected through a combination of community needs, project relevance, and societal impact. The focus on sustainability, health, and well-being guided the selection of challenges.

4.9 How teams were formed

The teams have been formed during the registration process. Nevertheless, during the event the teams have been mixed in accordance with the principles of design thinking methodology (diverse teams). All the participants have been willing to join their new teams and as a result great ideas have been created.

4.10 Team dynamics and collaboration

Collaborative dynamics were central to the Col-laborathon, with participants working together to transform ideas into action plans. The event's emphasis on co-creation, innovation, and collective learning fostered a collaborative spirit among diverse teams.

Figure 19. Catalonia Col-laborathon group dynamics, full room

4.11 Tools, frameworks, or methodologies used during the Col-laborathon

Figure 20. Catalonia Col-laborathon group dynamics into practice, in one group

The event's workshops, based on the SOAR methodology, the Social Innovation Canvas, provided alternatives for funding and replicability strategies, offering participants a space for debate, reflection, and collective creation. These workshops were at the heart of the event, where ideas were transformed into action plans and implementation strategies.

The talks at the event, like those by Maite Fibla from Ship2B Ventures and Adrià Buzón from Cuideo, were highlights, providing valuable perspectives on the financing of impact projects and business strategies for genuine social impact.

4.12 Overview of projects developed

Six projects were presented, including initiatives on emotional well-being for youth, healthy eating, virtual reality experiences for the elderly, musical education for babies, urban health impact assessment, and services for an ageing society. In the vibrant landscape of innovative initiatives, several standout projects are shaping the future of well-being and community engagement. These projects represent a diverse array of approaches, from fostering emotional well-being among youth to promoting sustainable eating and enhancing the quality of life for the elderly. Let's delve into these initiatives and explore their key features:

1. Youth Emotional Well-being Initiative:

Led by Oriol Huguet in collaboration with Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú and supported by Diputació de Barcelona, this project focuses on promoting emotional well-being among youth while creating essential connections with local resources.

2. FoodCLIC Project:

Under the leadership of Rosina Malagrida from LivingLab IrsiCaixa, the FoodCLIC project is dedicated to advocating healthy and sustainable eating in the neighbourhoods of the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona, demonstrating a strong commitment to community health and food sustainability.

3. VR360 Project for Elderly Well-being:

Spearheaded by David Gateu from Valls Genera, the VR360 project offers an immersive virtual reality experience tailored to the elderly, merging cutting-edge technology with social care to enhance their well-being.

4. Memima Baby App:

Albert Munne introduces us to the Memima Baby app, designed to introduce babies to the world of music, thereby fostering musical skills, language development, and creativity under parental guidance.

5. Healthy Cities Generator:

Presented by Marta Rofin from Bax & Company, the Healthy Cities Generator is an innovative online tool that evaluates the health impact of urban planning, offering practical insights into improving well-being through urban design.

6. SeniorLab Platform:

Karina Simieli presents SeniorLab, a collaborative platform aimed at redefining services and products for an ageing society, emphasising inclusivity and co-creation across different age groups.

4.13 Key features of selected projects

One of the most notable initiatives was led by Oriol Huguet and carried out by the Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú with support from the Diputació de Barcelona. This project focuses on promoting emotional well-being among youth, creating a bridge between them and the local resources available for their well-being. The FoodCLIC project, under the leadership of Rosina Malagrida from LivingLab IrsiCaixa, is another example of innovation. It focuses on healthy and sustainable eating in the neighbourhoods of the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona, receiving support from European and local projects, and showing a strong commitment to community health and food sustainability. In the field of well-being for the elderly, the VR360 project, led by David Gateu from Valls Genera, offers an immersive and sensory experience through virtual reality, allowing older people to virtually explore natural environments, an initiative that innovatively merges technology and social care. Albert Munne introduced us to Memima Baby, an app dedicated to musical education for babies. This tool allows parents to introduce their children to the world of music, fostering not only musical skills but also language development and creativity. Marta Rofin from Bax & Company introduced the Healthy Cities Generator, an online tool that assesses the health impact of urban planning. This project, selected as the most outstanding at the Col·laborathon, offers us an innovative and practical vision of how to improve health and well-being through urban design. Karina Simieli presented SeniorLab, a platform for redefining and co-creating services and products focused on an increasingly ageing society. This project stands out for its inclusive and collaborative approach, seeking to involve people of all ages in the design and development process.

As we can see, the initiatives presented share a strong focus on the well-being and health of various demographic groups, including young people, local communities, the elderly, and infants, promoting emotional well-being, physical health through sustainable eating, and the healthy impact of the urban environment. There is a tendency towards incorporating innovative technologies, such as the use of virtual reality and mobile applications to enhance the quality of life, highlighting the importance of innovation in well-being. Community commitment and co-creation are central pillars, seeking to actively involve communities and encourage participation in the development of solutions for an ageing society, as well as in promoting community health. Moreover, several initiatives address sustainability and environmental health, demonstrating the interconnection between environmental health and human well-being, through the evaluation of the health impact of urban planning policies and the promotion of healthy and sustainable eating. The inclusiveness and attention to various groups highlight the effort to create services and products that benefit the entire society, reflecting a holistic approach to well-being and innovation that emphasises the importance of technology, sustainability, community engagement, and inclusivity.

4.14 Criteria for judging projects

The event closed with a pitch contest where the evolution of the projects throughout the day could be observed, and the winning project was selected. The jury for the evaluation of the presented projects consisted of four distinguished individuals:

Mònica Boquera: An expert known for her proficiency and insights in the field relevant to the projects under assessment.

Mireia Sebastià: Possessing a wealth of experience and knowledge, Mireia Sebastià brought valuable perspectives to the evaluation process.

Empar Polo: Known for her expertise and contributions in relevant domains, Empar Polo likely provided valuable insights and assessments.

David Verde: With his expertise and experience, David Verde likely played a crucial role in evaluating the projects and providing recommendations for their improvement.

Each member of this jury likely brought a unique perspective and expertise to the evaluation process, contributing to a comprehensive and thorough assessment of the presented projects. Their combined insights would have helped in identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement across the projects, ultimately guiding decision-making and recommendations.

Evaluators provided constructive feedback on the presented initiatives, pointing out both potential and areas for improvement. They generally highlighted the appreciation of innovation and the potential impact of the initiatives, underlying the importance of replicability and sustainability. They acknowledged the reliance of some initiatives on public entities and warned of the challenges this may present. They also highlighted the need to include population segments that might not have access to necessary technology.

On the other hand, they valued the ability of certain initiatives to address cross-cutting problems and generate significant social impact. However, concerns persist about long-term viability in terms of costs and maintenance of these solutions. They also underscored the need for clearer impact measurement to assess the real effectiveness of the initiatives.

In conclusion, the assessment suggests a balance between praise for creativity and a call to attention to practical aspects such as financial sustainability and universal accessibility, as well as precision in evaluating results.

The conclusions and recommendations for the presented projects highlight several key areas of improvement and considerations for their success:

1. Xarxa Alison:

- Project Landing: Introduces the need for improvement in project landing, particularly in mindset and replicability. Thorough review of impact indicators is crucial for assessing effectiveness.
- Sustainability and Replicability: While the concept is innovative, enhancing replicability and addressing long-term sustainability concerns is essential for lasting impact, especially in rural settings.

2. FIRABEC:

- Dependence on Public Entities**: Significant reliance on public entities affects sustainability. Diversifying support sources is recommended for long-term stability.
- Originality and Population Segmentation**: Notes simplicity and ingenuity of the idea but suggests exploring opportunities to broaden its scope for medium-term sustainability.

3. MeMimaBaby:

- Market Competition: Identifies competition in the market and the need to address non-mobile phone users among the elderly. Inclusive solutions are recommended.

- Impact Assessment: Calls for clarification on how the project's impact is quantitatively and qualitatively assessed for demonstrating effectiveness.

4. Healthy Cities Generator:

- Cost of Use and Concept Definition: Clarity on project cost is needed for better understanding and acceptance.
- Short/Medium-Term Sustainability: Raises doubts about sustainability in the short to medium term, emphasising the importance of exploring sustainable strategies for viability.

5. SeniorLab:

- Impact Measurement and Organisational Sustainability: Calls for clarity in impact measurement and organisational sustainability beyond individual efforts.
- Digital Self-Sustainability: Recognizes potential impact but suggests exploring strategies for digital self-sustainability.

6. VR360:

- Unclear Business Model: Lack of clarity in the business model is highlighted as crucial for understanding viability.
- Competition and User Adherence: Concerns about competition and user retention raise questions about differentiation and long-term adherence. Demonstrating these aspects would be key for success.

The figure below shows the results for all participants MVP prioritization, besides that was an evaluation by jury assessment (4 experts).

Figure 21. Catalonia Col·laborathon proposals presented and its evaluation

Direct the model towards emphasis on replicability and sustainability across all projects, clarity in impact indicators, attention to competition and differentiation for user retention, clear business models, and ethical considerations such as inclusion. These areas are critical and have been identified as priorities for the long-term success of social initiatives.

4.15 Any follow-up initiatives or plans

The positive feedback from participants suggests the potential for future collaborations and innovation events in the region. The standout project, the Healthy Cities Generator, is expected to be explored further, indicating a commitment to transforming cities into healthier and more sustainable environments.

4.16 Quotes or feedback from participants, mentors or organisers

At the end of the Col-laborathon, 33 out of the total 56 participants completed a survey form, rating and adding comments related to the day's events. This survey, comprising 12 questions, gathered comprehensive feedback from participants, mentors, and organisers, offering a detailed insight into their experiences and perceptions. Here is an analysis of the responses to each of these questions, reflecting on the various aspects of the event as evaluated by those who took part.

- **Content adequacy:** The participants rated the adequacy of the day's content with an average of 4 out of 5, indicating that the content effectively met the objectives of the day. This suggests a strong alignment between the event's goals and the delivered content.
- **Takeaways from the event:** Participants shared a range of valuable takeaways, including establishing new contacts, acquiring knowledge, gaining insights into social financing, and discovering business proposals with social impact. These responses highlight the event's role as a catalyst for networking, learning, and inspiration in social innovation and entrepreneurship.
- **Proposal dynamics:** The dynamics of the proposals were rated an average of 4.24 out of 5, reflecting that the event's activities and methodologies were engaging and promoted active participation among attendees.
- **Networking time:** Opinions on whether there was enough time for networking were divided, with 20 participants responding 'yes' and 13 'no'. This feedback points to a need for potentially reevaluating the event's schedule to allow for more networking opportunities.
- **Organisation and motivation by the team:** The organising team's efforts in managing and motivating participants were acknowledged with an average rating of 4.18 out of 5. This indicates a high level of satisfaction with the event's organisation and the team's ability to engage participants.
- **Duration and dedication for initiative development:** Participants felt that the duration and dedication provided for developing initiatives were somewhat insufficient, reflected in the average rating of 3.55 out of 5. This suggests room for improvement in event planning to allow more time for initiative development.
- **Expectations for the INTEGER project:** The survey revealed that participants have high expectations for the INTEGER project, looking forward to learning about and participating in impactful social innovation projects, fostering a culture of innovation, and promoting local initiatives.

- **Future actions for the INTEGER project:** Suggestions for future actions included organising more events, enhancing dissemination efforts, implementing specific training methodologies, and creating more inclusive and accessible activities. These recommendations indicate a desire for continued engagement and expansion of the project's activities.
- **Interest of the initiative for the territory:** A significant majority (31 out of 33 respondents) believe the initiative is of interest to the territory, highlighting its potential to make a positive impact on the local context.
- **Areas for improvement:** Feedback on areas for improvement focused on better inclusion of the public sector, optimising the event's timing, and emphasising non-profit actions. Participants also suggested providing more support materials and improving the understanding of projects prior to the event.
- **Improvement suggestions:** Participants suggested various improvements such as more focus on the public sector, keeping times, and providing more time for completing tasks. They also mentioned the need for more information on projects beforehand and better facilitation of workshops.
- **Additional comments or suggestions:** Some participants offered congratulations, while others suggested improvements for catering or expressed a desire to develop a product and be part of the next edition.

The diversity of institutions represented by the respondents, including government/administration (36.36%), industry/private sector (24.24%), academia/research (18.18%), and civil society/citizens (21.21%), underscores the wide interest and potential impact of the Col-laborathon and the INTEGER project across different sectors.

4.17 Detailed information on challenges, projects, or methodologies

The methodology employed for the session involved three key components: SOAR, PITCH, and SOCIAL BUSINESS MODEL CANVA.

1. **SOAR:** This acronym stands for Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results. It's a strategic planning framework that focuses on identifying and leveraging strengths and opportunities to achieve aspirations and desired results. During the session, participants likely analysed these elements to gain insights into their current situation and future potential.

2. **PITCH:** This likely refers to the act of presenting or pitching ideas, projects, or proposals. It involves succinctly communicating key points, benefits, and objectives to an audience. Participants may have been tasked with crafting and delivering pitches related to their projects or initiatives as part of the session.

3. **SOCIAL BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS:** This is likely a reference to using the Business Model Canvas framework specifically tailored for social enterprises or businesses with a social mission. The Business Model Canvas is a visual tool used to describe, design, challenge, and pivot business models. In the context of social enterprises, it helps organisations map out their value proposition, target audience, revenue streams, key activities, partnerships, and more, with a focus on creating social impact alongside financial sustainability.

In summary, the session likely involved strategic planning using the SOAR framework, crafting and delivering pitches, and utilizing the Social Business Model Canvas to design or refine business models with a social impact focus.

The [tools and materials](#) utilized during the Catalonia Col-laborathon have been successfully uploaded to the [Integer platform](#). These resources are now accessible for social innovators seeking to integrate them into the development of their projects.

Figure 22. Discussion Tables presented to the stakeholders during the event

The images gathered from the various working groups likely capture elements of these activities, such as brainstorming sessions, presentations, or visual representations of business models.

Figure 23. Discussion and Dynamics during Catalonia Col-laborathon

Figure 24. Discussion and Dynamics results from Catalonia Col-laborathon

4.18 News on the INTEGER website

The dissemination managers together with the Catalan partners have prepared news to disseminate the event on the INTEGER website

Exciting day at the INTEGER Regional Col-laborathon in Tarragona!

Today, we are thrilled to witness the convergence of minds from the Quadruple Helix. INTEGER is bringing together 50 agents determined to propel impactful social projects.

Big kudos to our partners, **Universitat Rovira i Virgili** and **i2CAT Foundation**, for orchestrating diverse activities aimed at fostering collaboration and sparking groundbreaking solutions.

At the event, **Rafael Nualart**, Digital Innovation Manager at **i2CAT Foundation**, introduced the INTEGER project, aiming to establish pioneering European living labs aligned with the new Innovation agenda, all aimed at enhancing citizens' health and wellbeing. Rafael shared, "INTEGER aspires to generate living labs at the European level based on the new European innovation agenda to improve the health and well-being of citizens."

Xavier Camara-Turull, researcher at **Universitat Rovira i Virgili**, delineated the Col-laborathon's objectives and the agenda for the day, emphasizing the initiative's dedication to catalyzing social innovation through the collaborative efforts of Quadruple Helix agents. Xavier remarked, "The Col-laborathon aims to promote social innovation initiatives through the collaboration of Quadruple Helix agents."

Stay tuned for more updates! We will be back soon with further news and insights about this event. Keep an eye out for exciting developments!

#INTEGER #SocialInnovation #QuadrupleHelix #Collaboration #EuropeanInnovation #HealthAndWellBeing #Collaboration #InnovationLeadership #Tarragona #Spain

Carina Dantas, Natália Machado Inês Saavedra, Joana Vieira SHINE 2Europe Toñi Caro, Chris O. Moscardini Lucuriaga Rafael Nualart, Marcos Doespiritusanto Gallego, Wilkeke Van Staalsduinen, Javier Ganzarain, Jonas Bernitt AFEdemy, age-friendly environments academy, Uniwersytet Jagielloński w Krakowie, Kai Schnackenberg, Rachel Stenner, Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg, Monika Machowska, Agnieszka Włodarczyk, Mateusz Kowacki Krakowski Park Technologiczny | Krakow Technology Park, Lina Silveira, F6S

Figure 25. The information shared by SHINE partner in LinkedIn about Catalan initiatives

Catalonia Col-laborathon: Catalyzing Innovation and Impactful Solutions for Health and Wellbeing

By Federico / November 25, 2023

During an atmosphere pulsating with innovation and collaboration, the Catalonia Col-laborathon unfolded as a dynamic convergence of minds, dedicated to steering impactful social initiatives within the realm of health and well-being. Hosted on November 22, in Tortosa, Spain, this event brought together its groundbreaking social initiatives, fostering an environment primed for co-creation and the birth of new solutions.

INTEGER, the driving force behind this event, orchestrated the gathering of 50 dedicated agents, united in their mission to propel impactful social projects forward. Partners Universitat Rovira i Virgili and QCAT Foundation played instrumental roles in orchestrating a series of activities aimed at fostering collaboration and nurturing groundbreaking solutions.

Rafael Huastec, Digital Innovation Manager at QCAT Foundation, introduced the INTEGER project, aiming to establish pioneering European living labs, focused on enhancing citizens' health and wellbeing. He stressed, "INTEGER aspires to generate living labs at the European level based on the new European Innovation agenda to improve the health and well-being of citizens." Xavier Càmara-Torral, a researcher at Universitat Rovira i Virgili, outlined the Col-laborathon's objectives, highlighting its commitment to catalyzing social innovation through collaboration among Guàrdia Health Agents.

Following an inspiring session presenting challenges and local use cases, experts and participants delved into action, forming diverse groups to tackle the "Health and Wellness for Life" challenge in Catalonia. These dynamic teams engaged in co-creation, crafting innovative and tangible solutions. Simultaneously, a focus group explored how the INTEGER Health collaborative framework could amplify its impact, fostering enlightening discussions and idea exchange.

Aritz Buzón Luqui, representing Guàrdia, delivered a compelling talk on "From Economic Benefits to Social Impact: Business Strategies With Real Social Impact." Guàrdia's challenge of enabling older individuals to maintain independence at home through tailored services, leveraging new technologies.

Marta Fàbregas, representing Sospita Ventana, shared insights on innovative financing, emphasizing the incorporation of Sustainable Development Goals into business agendas and the pivotal role of technology in social innovation.

Attendees also participated in specialized training sessions, empowering them with skills crucial in presenting projects to investors, ensuring recognition for social impact and growth potential.

The event culminated in a pitch contest, where participants showcased their projects and Market Value Propositions developed during workshops, applying INTEGER's processes and dynamics to drive impactful social projects.

The INTEGER Regional Col-laborathon of Catalonia in Tortosa was a testament to collaborative efforts, innovative ideas, and transformative discussions. Participants left energized and inspired, armed with the tools to drive change and create a better future.

A heartfelt thank to all who joined, making this day an incredible journey of innovation and collective impact.

For more updates and insights from INTEGER initiatives, stay connected with us.

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Figure 26. The information shared by SHINE partner in INTEGER website about Catalan initiatives

5 Final Col-laborathon event

5.1 Overview of the event

The Final Col-laborathon inter-regional event, that engaged not only the highest ranked projects presented during the regional col-labs but also representatives of the stakeholders in the 3 different regions. It took place online on the 17th of January and it had a balanced agenda that not only presented the outcomes and results of the regional event, as it had as well a inspirational talk, by an invited expert in finances, as well as the pitch presentation from the regional proposals (the highest ranked per region) and announcement of the winner of the three of them.

The criteria used for the evaluation were 3, as used as well in the three regional events: Concept & innovation; Sustainability & replicability and Impact. Regarding the **“Concept & innovation”**, the participants had to demonstrate a clear set of objectives aligned with the definition of the goals and with the general objectives of the INTEGER project and the Col-laborathon challenge. Appropriateness of the project scope as the overall project vision. Quality, credibility, and clarity of project description. Interoperability level of the proposed solution. Innovation level, not only in a technical perspective, but also in a strategic and implementation perspective, as well as practices. On the **“Sustainability & replicability”** criteria quality, effectiveness and clarity of project activities and its sustainability & replicability was the focus. As well as the alignment of the activities/actions with the INTEGER goals and the SDG goals. Presentation of milestones and means of verification. Finally, in the **“Impact”**, the proposal had to define its ambition and a clear set of expectations aligned with the objectives of the Col-laborathon. Proposals had also to demonstrate the impact of the proposal and its contribution. The ambition underlines the potential extent and overall impact of the proposal actions. The challenge was to present each of these points in a pitching style followed by a Q&A moment led by the evaluators. The final agenda is in the below image, with details of the timings and speakers.

Final event - Col-laborathon	
17th of January, 2024	
AGENDA	
Moderator: Lina Silveira, F6S	
10h30	Welcome and introduction, Lina Silveira, F6S (5m)
10h35	Overall goals Work Package 3, Xiaoni Li, URV (10m)
10h45	Col-laborathon model & the platform, Tofii Caro & Rafel Naluart, I2CAT (10m)
10h50	Summary of the Col-laborathon of Catalonia, Xiaoni Li, URV (7m)
11h00	Summary of the Col-laborathon of Krakow, Mateusz Kowacki, KTP, (7m)
11h05	Summary of the Col-laborathon of Hamburg, Kai Schnackenberg, HAM (7m)
11h10	Present the pool of evaluators & the methodology, Lina Silveira, F6S (10m) Evaluators: Mireia Sebastià (Catalonia), Marcus Falke (Hamburg) and Jolanta Perek-Białas (Krakow).
11h20	Highest ranked projects presentation: a) Highest ranked project in Catalonia, Celia Garcia, Healthy Cities (5m) - Q&A, 5 min b) Highest ranked project in Krakow, Tomasz Rębkowski, Sądziadex, (5m) - Q&A, 5 min c) Highest ranked project in Hamburg, Annika Bruhns-Peterson; Antje Kallweit, start-up company help, (5m) - Q&A, 5 min
12h00	Alternative strategies to finance social innovation, Josep Biosca Ship28 (15m)
12h15	Present the final result - the winner project, Lina Silveira (F6S) & brief comment from evaluator(s) & winner (10m)
12h25	Lessons learnt and closing notes, Xiaoni Li, URV (5m)
<i>Note: Times mentioned are only indicative</i>	

Figure 27. The final agenda of the inter-regional Final Col-laborathon of the 17th of January 2024

During the pitching session each evaluator had to score each of the criteria's from 1 to 5, and the score was accessed as the following:

- 0 = Proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information;
- 1 = Poor: criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses;
- 2 = Fair: proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses;
- 3 = Good: proposal addresses the criterion well, but a small number of shortcomings is present;
- 4 = Very good: proposal addresses the criterion very well, a reasonable number of shortcomings is present;
- 5 = Excellent: proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

Each evaluator was requested to provide a comment for each proposal, as an added value to provide to the project presenters, about the strength and weaknesses that they assessed in the proposal. These comments were made available by the regional partner after the event, however the result of the evaluation and announcement of the winner was made at the end of the event, congratulating the winner that in this case was the Catalonian project. The decision was made as well as a product of the discussion and agreement between the evaluators that had the opportunity to discuss in a separate room the final conclusions and scores. You can see in the final table extracted from google form the results and details of the evaluation below, with the comments and the provided scores per criteria, as well as the final score.

Proposals	CRITERIA			FINAL SCORE	Comments
	Concept & innovation	Sustainability & replicability	Impact		
CATALONIA: Celia Garcia, Healthy Cities	5	4	4	4.333333333	Addresses a global issue of congestion and design for a more sustainable society in every aspect ; Marketing and cost topic as health of citizens in cities are important. I like that it is linked to AFCC and SDG, based on science, advanced already; it is advanced and so more time (years) and funds to prepare it was involved, as not as new idea during the event, not everything was presented structural approach so with great pontial for deep impact; other countries, other circumstances so the replicability could be difficult
KRAKOW: Tomasz Rebkowski, Sasiadex	3	3	3	3	Our population is aging, and it is a highly inclusive and valuable proposal; topic as the need is real, exclusion of older persons to be mobile, real problem- real solution, and also as a fresh new not experienced group of not professionals prepared it;) ; direct benefit for the people
HAMBURG: Annika Bruhns-Petersson; Antje Kallweit, start-up company help	4	4	4	4	Every day, more players emerge to address health in a digital and AI-supported manner; Tayto is a solution that would be in this new approach to healthcare; great organization, clear and important topic as a digital application highly replicable, scaleable

Figure 28. The name of the proposals per region, scores and comments of the evaluators during the inter-regional Final Col-laborathon of the 17th of January 2024

Each project received a logo to be used and disseminated associating them to the INTEGER project and finalists of the INTEGER competition. This association with the project has proven to be very interesting to the stakeholders, by providing validation and credibility to their project proposals.

5.2 News on INTEGER website and social media

The dissemination managers together with the partners have prepared news to disseminate the event on the INTEGER website.

INTEGER - Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in...
 328 seguidores
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News from INTEGER Col-laborathon Grand Finale! 🎉

We are happy to share that yesterday marked the grand finale of the INTEGER Col-laborathon, and what an incredible journey it has been! 🌍

During this event with 28 participants, we delved into the goals of WP3, the innovative Col-laborathon model, and our platform. We also had a chance to learn more about the Col-laborathons conducted in the ecosystems of INTEGER: Catalonia, Krakow, and Hamburg.

A special highlight was the presentation of the remarkable winners of each ecosystem, who showcased their visionary projects:

- 🏆 **Healthy Cities.** (Celia Garcia) - Catalonia: A groundbreaking tool focusing on urban health and wellbeing – the Healthy Cities generator.
- 🏆 **Sąsiadex** (Tomasz Rebkowski) - Krakow: Revolutionizing car sharing for individuals commuting to work, enabling older adults to reach medical appointments and other crucial engagements.
- 🏆 Start-up company **HELP Mee Schmerztherapie GmbH** (Annika Bruhns-Peterson and Dr. Antje Kallweit) - Hamburg: Introducing digital pain therapy with a fresh objective – unlearn chronic pain to achieve wellness, all through an innovative app.

As we explored alternative strategies to finance social innovation with insights from Josep Biosca from the **Ship2B Ventures** Foundation, our evaluators deliberated on the winners based on criteria such as Concept & Innovation, Sustainability & Replicability, and Impact.

🎉 Congratulations to the winner: **Healthy Cities!** We are thrilled to award them the INTEGER label as the winner, along with accolades for finalists. This recognition is our commitment to supporting further development and fundraising initiatives. We extend our congratulations to the exceptional efforts and initiatives presented by all the finalists, as well.

You can join this movement by accessing our free platform: <https://lnkd.in/d7wQ2aP2!> 🌐 In this digital participatory space, you can connect with like-minded organizations, explore networking opportunities, and embark on social innovation projects tackling real challenges alongside the 4 helix stakeholders.

#INTEGER #InnovationInAction
 Carina Dantas, Natália Machado, Inês Saavedra, Joana Vieira - SHINE 2Europe,
 Toñi Caro, Chris O. Moscardi Luzuriaga, Rafael Nualart, Marcos Doespiritusanto Gallego - I2CAT
 Willeke Van Staalduinen, Javier Ganzarain, Jonas Bernitt - AFEdemy, age-friendly environments academy
 Lina Silveira - F6S
 Xavier Camara-Turull - Universitat Rovira i Virgili
 Kai Schnackenberg, Rachel Stenner - Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg,
 Monika Machowska, Agnieszka Włodarczyk, Mateusz Kowacki - Krakowski Park Technologiczny | Krakow Technology Park, Uniwersytet Jagielloński w Krakowie

Figure 29. The information shared by SHINE partner in LinkedIn about Col-laborathon Grand Finale

INTEGER Col-laborathon Grand Finale

By Frederico / January 20, 2024

On January 17, 2024, the INTEGER Col-laborathon reached its conclusion, marking a collaborative and innovative journey involving 28 participants in an online event.

Lina Silveira from F6S facilitated the event and handed over the floor to Xiaoni Li (Universitat Rovira i Virgili), who provided insights into WPS goals and main tasks. Toni Caro, the project coordinator from i2CAT, shared the Col-laborathon model, and Rafel Nulart (i2CAT) presented the platform, referred to as a "digital participatory space." This session included a summary of the regional events previously held in the three ecosystems: Catalonia (Xiaoni Li), Krakow (Mateusz Kowacki – Krakow Technology Park), and Hamburg (Kai Schnackenberg – The Ministry of Social Affairs of the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg).

The winning projects from each ecosystem were presented as follows:

- [Healthy Cities Generator](#) – Bax & Company – from Catalonia (Celia Garcia): Introducing a tool focusing on urban health and wellbeing, the Healthy Cities generator.
- [Szipladex](#) from Krakow (Tomasz Reblowski): Revolutionizing car sharing for commuting individuals, aiding older adults in Poland.
- [Start-up company HELP Me](#) from Hamburg (Annika Bruhns-Petersson and Antje Kallweit): Presenting digital pain therapy through an innovative app.

Attendees explored alternative financing strategies with powerful insights from Josep Bisca of the SHIP2B Foundation while evaluators selected winners based on Concept & Innovation, Sustainability & Replicability, and Impact.

Congratulations to the winner, Healthy Cities Generator! The INTEGER team will provide the winner's label and accolades to finalists, reaffirming our commitment to supporting development and fundraising. Special congratulations to all finalists for their outstanding efforts.

Xiaoni Li concluded the session with final notes and lessons learned, highlighting that "The regional events worked as a collaborative learning hub. [...] The events allowed the regions to find common ground and share insights and lessons learned that will support each region to adjust and implement their programs in their regions."

Join the project on our platform, [INTEGER Platform](#), where you can connect with like-minded organizations, explore networking opportunities, and engage in social innovation projects tackling real challenges alongside the 4 helix stakeholders.

Figure 30. The information shared by SHINE partner in INTEGER website about Col-laborathon Grand Finale

After the INTEGER Col-laborathon grand finale we provided the participants of a participation seal

Figure 31. Digital award for the selected initiative

This seal is perceived by the partners of INTEGER project as well by the winner as an added value that provides credibility and recognition of the project proposals, as they were evaluated and selected by experts and their project recognized as a valuable solution for their regions and inter-regional participants.

6 Conclusions

These 3 regional events presented an opportunity to get to know better the ecosystem and also to connect it with the international ecosystem, by bridging their actions to the other regions in the INTEGER project, allowing the regional stakeholders to reflect on their actions, their state of the art, as well as the difference and similarities in terms of needs and challenges. We describe in each region what are the conclusions and lessons learned that these events provided to the regional partners and their ecosystem.

The lessons learned from the Krakow Col-laborathon started by the identification of Strategic Collaboration that combined the regional Col-laborathon with the Life Science Open Space conference proved to be a strategic success. This collaboration helped create a substantial critical mass for the event, resulting in over 300 attendees. Additionally, the Quadruple Helix Engagement was also a valuable point, as the involvement of stakeholders from the quadruple helix (students, seniors, business professionals, administrators, and academic individuals) played a crucial role. This engagement was a key objective and significantly contributed to the success of the Col-laborathon.

Another success point of the event was on the publicity of the objectives achieved, as the Col-laborathon successfully met its objectives, including generating publicity for the INTEGER project. The event's unique approach and collaboration efforts attracted attention, fulfilling one of the primary goals.

The collaborative efforts during the event led to the creation of five innovative ideas for social initiatives. Remarkably, one of these ideas is slated for implementation as a pilot project in a municipality in the Malopolska Region, allowing the project impact to go beyond its implementation, as a seed that proved to be valuable for the future of the ecosystem development.

An important point to stress out in the Krakow event is that there was an effort to ensure interdisciplinarity and diversity in team composition and it proved beneficial. As age diversity in Teams was ensured, as it comprised individuals across a wide age range (23-82) that benefited the fostering a rich exchange of perspectives and ideas.

Also, it was beneficial to use tools such as Design Thinking, taking into account that the application of design thinking methodology was instrumental in providing a productive exchange of ideas. Facilitators from Krakow Technology Park and Jagiellonian University, with expertise in design thinking, contributed to the success of the workshops and collaborative processes. As well as the AHathon Format, as the format of the AHathon, structured as a co-creation and collaboration workshop for social innovations, proved effective. The incorporation of yoga classes, leisure corners, and breaks created an environment conducive to creative thinking.

Another point worth highlighting was the Active Healthy Aging focus, as the Col-laborathon focus on addressing challenges related to the ageing population, especially in cities, aligned with the societal need in Poland. This emphasis on social innovation showcased the event's relevance and impact. Earning and adjusting the thematics to the needs of the ecosystem proved to be very beneficial.

Regarding the selection of the project, one of the points that was positive was the judging Criteria, as they were clear judging criteria, addressing points as concept and innovation, sustainability, replicability, and impact. These criterias were instrumental in evaluating and selecting winning projects. Additionally, considerations for alignment with SDG goals were incorporated so that there was an international browder alignment with the regional projects to the international goals.

In a post-event perspective, we can stress that the winning team's prize package included professional mentoring and financial support for pilot implementation, and it served as a post-event initiative to encourage the development and implementation of innovative solutions.

These lessons provide valuable insights for future Col-laborathons and underscore the importance of strategic planning, stakeholder engagement, and a focus on addressing real societal challenges.

As a conclusion for Hamburg, the Hamburg Col-laborathon brought together stakeholders from the four helixes and explored social innovation topics in greater depth.

Innovations from start-up companies were presented in the pitch session. A company was chosen as the champion whose innovation is highly relevant and whose many people suffer from chronic pain. Sustainability was an important criterion. The company is aiming to be included in the DIGA directory, which lists digital healthcare services in Germany that are reimbursed by health insurance companies. This will ensure a long-term business model.

In the work stores, the idea of living labs from the other pilot regions was examined and the benefits in the Hamburg ecosystem were discussed. Great potential for a Hamburg Living Lab was seen particularly in the context of local health centers, in which innovative primary care is tested at a local level. With this in mind, further meetings and workshops were planned in order to promote this idea beyond the Col-laborathon.

In the case of the conclusions and lessons Learned from the Catalonia Col-laborathon, an ecosystem that proved to have a more mature ecosystem with several actions already taking place in the region and a better knowledge between the stakeholders we can mention several points that these events added to the ecosystem creation and strengthening, as the diverse Initiatives that were implemented, as the Catalonia Col-laborathon showcased a diverse range of projects addressing issues related to sustainable development, health, and well-being. This diversity reflects the multifaceted challenges in the community and the potential for innovative solutions. showcasing as well the diverse needs between regions, as it did not address just one point as the other regions did.

Another important point of conclusion is the value of collaborative learning, as the event served as a platform for collective learning, allowing participants to gain insights into various projects and initiatives. The presentations and workshops facilitated knowledge sharing and collaboration among attendees.

This event gave the opportunity to give the floor to impactful and successful Initiatives, such as those focused on emotional well-being for youth, healthy eating, virtual reality for the elderly, musical education for babies, urban health assessment, and services for an aging society, demonstrating the potential for social impact through innovative approaches.

As it was the case in the other regions, the methodological Approaches also gave a positive input in providing effective tools for developing action plans and implementation strategies, as it was the case in Catalonia with the use of the SOAR methodology and the Social Innovation Canvas in workshops. These methodologies fostered a structured approach to idea transformation.

This event was also an opportunity to provide value oftTalks, as it enabled the talks by industry experts on financing impact projects and business strategies that provided social impact added value to the event. Insights from Maite Fibla and Adrià Buzón contributed valuable perspectives on navigating the social impact landscape.

One of the conclusions is that the evaluator feedback emphasised the importance of innovation, potential impact, replicability, and sustainability. The evaluation highlighted the need for solutions to address cross-cutting problems and generate significant social impact while addressing challenges related to costs and maintenance, validating, and providing guidance to the presented solutions.

One valuable point to take out from this event is the population Inclusivity, as the evaluators underscored the need for inclusivity, cautioning about potential limitations when relying on public entities and emphasising the importance of reaching population segments that may not have access to necessary technology.

The Catalonia event showed the importance of balancing creativity and practicality, as the evaluation findings revealed a balance between praising creativity and raising attention to practical aspects such as financial sustainability, universal accessibility, and precision in evaluating results. A valuable input that will allow a fresh and useful perspective to the project owners.

It is important to stress that the overall attendees had a positive assessment of the Col-laborathon, highlighting the relevance of the event, the connections made, and the knowledge gained. Despite suggestions for improvement, the event was perceived as a significant step in promoting social and digital innovation in Catalonia. The Cataluna Col-laborathon was perceived as a catalyst for Innovation of ideas and projects, promoting the creation of a platform for collaboration, idea exchange, and strategic alliances that went even beyond the Catalonia region, bridging them to other regions. The success of Marta Rofin's Healthy Cities Generator exemplifies the event's potential to transform cities into healthier and more sustainable environments, with an inter-regional validation of its value beyond the Catalonia region.

The event demonstrated that stakeholders that participated in the event left with satisfaction and enthusiasm, expressing optimism for future collaborations and innovation initiatives in the region. The positive feedback sets a promising precedent for future endeavours in fostering a robust innovation ecosystem in Catalonia.

7 REFERENCES

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